

Visual AIS Type Verification: A Non-Cooperative Approach to Maritime Security

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Abstract—The Automatic Identification System (AIS) is cooperative: it fails when vessels disable transponders, spoof identities, or lack equipment. We propose visual AIS type verification, a non-cooperative approach where camera imagery independently checks whether observed vessel types match AIS expectations. AIS context defines a dynamic white-list of expected types, framing verification as context-dependent Out-of-Distribution (OOD) detection. Our three-stage pipeline (detection, type recognition, set-level verification) is evaluated on 186 crops from 43 vessels in German coastal waters. SigLIP2 logistic regression on white-list reference photos achieves 70.6% accuracy across 9 vessel types with an Area Under the ROC Curve (AUROC) of 0.844 for flagging unknown vessels; SigLIP2 zero-shot reaches 68.7% without any reference data. On clean imagery, zero-shot accuracy reaches 94.6%, confirming that recognition capability is not the bottleneck but operational imaging conditions are. We also find that bearing-based AIS association achieves only 30.6% precision, depressing measured accuracy by 25 pp and motivating set-level verification over per-vessel matching.

I. INTRODUCTION

Maritime surveillance depends on the Automatic Identification System (AIS) for vessel identity and type [1], but AIS is cooperative: it works only when vessels transmit truthful data. Deliberate manipulation such as transponder disabling and identity spoofing is a documented tool of sanctions evasion and smuggling [2], [3]. Camera-based perception offers a non-cooperative alternative. Existing camera-AIS fusion [4], [5] detects vessels as a single class and derives type information entirely from AIS after spatial association, implicitly trusting AIS declarations. Both use stationary shore-based cameras; from a moving vessel, ship motion and low elevation make per-vessel bearing matching impractical, further motivating a set-level approach. Ship type recognition has been studied on curated datasets [6], but not integrated with AIS verification under operational conditions.

We propose visual AIS type verification using a dynamic white-list: AIS reports which vessel types should be visible, defining an in-distribution boundary. Visual detections not matching this expected set trigger Out-of-Distribution (OOD) alerts [7]. Unlike fixed OOD boundaries, ours is constructed per-observation from an external signal. Consider a Vessel Traffic Service (VTS) operator monitoring a waterway: AIS indicates a container ship and a passenger vessel, but the camera classifies three vessels as container, passenger, and tanker. The discrepancy flags an anomaly for investigation.

Our contributions: (1) A three-stage pipeline (detection, type recognition, set-level verification) requiring no per-vessel

bearing matching. (2) A white-list approach using 2,368 ship-spotting photographs for 50 vessels. (3) A finding that bearing-based annotation achieves only 30.6% precision, depressing accuracy by 25 pp and motivating set-level verification. (4) An upper-bound analysis (94.6% on clean imagery) confirming methods work but operational conditions are the bottleneck.

II. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Our pipeline has three stages: detection localizes all vessels, type recognition classifies each crop, and set-level verification compares the visual types against AIS expectations. Fig. 1 illustrates these stages on real data.

Detection: RF-DETR Large [8] fine-tuned on the Maritime Collision Avoidance dataset [9] and evaluated at 1664×1664 resolution detects all vessels, producing crops regardless of vessel type.

Type recognition compares three approaches (Table I): zero-shot, reference-based, and a generative VLM. They are built on pre-trained models. CLIP [10] and SigLIP2 [11] are image-text models that embed an image and a short text description into a shared space, so a crop can be classified by the description it best matches, while DINOv3 [12] is an image-only encoder used for matching against labelled examples. *Zero-shot* needs no reference data: each crop is matched by cosine similarity to per-class text prototypes, which are author-written, each averaging 8–12 text embeddings: 4 templates (e.g., "a photograph of a vessel at sea") filled with 2–3 descriptive phrases per class (e.g., "tugboat", "harbor tug"). *Reference-based* instead matches crops against a support set of the 2,368 ship-spotting photographs; we favour the compact DINOv3 ViT-S/16 (22M parameters) for eventual edge deployment on vessel-mounted hardware, and train the logistic-regression variant with balanced class weights. The VLM prompts Qwen2.5-VL-7B [13] with the image and the 9 type names. Out-of-distribution detection uses Maximum Softmax Probability (MSP) [7]. Zero-shot and the VLM require no reference data, enabling immediate deployment, while reference-based trades a photo database for higher accuracy on white-listed vessels. All three add new vessel types without retraining: zero-shot and the VLM by adding text descriptions, reference-based by adding photographs.

Set-level verification compares the multiset of visually predicted types $\hat{\mathcal{V}}$ against AIS-expected types \mathcal{A} , producing three outputs (Fig. 4): TYPE MATCH (consistent), TYPE MISMATCH (unexpected type or count), UNKNOWN VESSEL

Fig. 1. Visual pipeline on real data from a vessel-mounted PTZ camera in the Weser estuary. Scene selected for type diversity within a single image. (a) Detection: bounding boxes around all vessels. (b) Type recognition: crops classified with confidence. (c) Set-level verification: visual types compared against AIS-expected types, flagging the anomaly.

TABLE I

TYPE RECOGNITION METHODS, ORDERED BY APPROACH AS IN FIG. 2. SIGLIP2 SERVES BOTH THE ZERO-SHOT AND REFERENCE-BASED APPROACHES; DINOv3 IS IMAGE-ONLY.

Method	Model	Approach	Classifies by
SigLIP2 ZS	SigLIP2 ViT-SO400M/14	Zero-shot	cosine sim. to text prototypes
CLIP ZS	CLIP ViT-L/14	Zero-shot	cosine sim. to text prototypes
SigLIP2 LR	SigLIP2 ViT-SO400M/14	Reference	logistic regression on ref. photos
DINOv3 kNN-5	DINOv3 ViT-S/16	Reference	majority vote, 5 nearest ref. photos
DINOv3 Proto	DINOv3 ViT-S/16	Reference	nearest ref.-photo prototype
Qwen VLM	Qwen2.5-VL-7B	VLM	generates type name

TABLE II

ACCURACY UNDER FOUR ANNOTATION QUALITY LEVELS. ORIGINAL: RAW AUTOMATIC BEARING ASSOCIATIONS. CORRECTED: WRONG VESSEL ASSIGNMENTS MANUALLY FIXED. VERIFIED: ONLY CROPS WITH MANUALLY CONFIRMED ASSOCIATIONS. REVIEWED: ALL 186 CROPS INDIVIDUALLY REVIEWED, EXCLUDING AMBIGUOUS CASES.

Slice	N (ID)	SigLIP2 LR	SigLIP2 ZS	DINOv3 kNN-5	CLIP ZS
Original	103	45.6%	44.7%	53.4%	33.0%
Corrected	159	48.4%	47.8%	56.0%	37.1%
Verified	95	55.8%	54.7%	60.0%	45.3%
Reviewed	163	70.6%	68.7%	69.3%	49.7%

(max class probability below threshold, indicating OOD). The OOD boundary is non-stationary, adapting per-observation to AIS context. No per-vessel bearing matching is required.

III. EVALUATION

A. Dataset and Annotation

We evaluate on 296 images from a vessel-mounted Pan-Tilt-Zoom (PTZ) camera ($13\times-100\times$ zoom, 498–9974 m range) aboard BSH (Federal Maritime and Hydrographic Agency) research vessel Atair in the Weser estuary. Unlike harbor-based datasets that can be collected from fixed land installations, this data represents the more challenging and scarce vessel-mounted coastal scenario with varying viewpoints, distances, and atmospheric conditions. RF-DETR produces 282 detections; after bearing-based AIS association and manual quality review, we obtain 186 crops from 43 vessels: 163 in-distribution (9 types) and 23 OOD. The support set contains 2,368 photographs for 50 vessels.

Ground truth was obtained via bearing-based AIS association (camera azimuth combined with own-ship GPS; Hungarian algorithm on angular error). This is used only for annotation; deployment uses set-level verification. Only 15 of 49 automatically matched crops (30.6%) were correctly

associated. Table II shows the impact of annotation quality across four progressively cleaner slices: accuracy improves monotonically for all methods, with SigLIP2 LR rising from 45.6% to 70.6%. This demonstrates that annotation noise is the dominant source of measured error, not recognition failure.

B. Classification and OOD Detection

Table III reports accuracy, macro-F1, and OOD detection on the reviewed set (Fig. 2). SigLIP2 LR achieves the best accuracy (70.6%) and AUROC (0.844) for flagging unknown vessels via MSP (Fig. 3). At an operating point of 80% true positive rate, the false positive rate is approximately 30%, potentially acceptable for a screening context where alerts trigger operator review. The accuracy/macro-F1 gap reflects class imbalance: three types (tanker $n=4$, dredger $n=5$, pilot $n=6$) have near-zero recall, while the six largest classes (container 46, cargo 39, passenger 24, tug 19, patrol 12, research 8) perform substantially better. Yet the dominant failure mode is cargo/container ship confusion, expected given their visual similarity.

Fig. 2. Classification accuracy on the reviewed set (163 ID crops), grouped by approach (zero-shot, reference-based, VLM).

TABLE III
VESSEL TYPE CLASSIFICATION ACCURACY, MACRO-F1, AND OOD DETECTION AUROC ON THE REVIEWED SET (163 ID, 23 OOD CROPS).

Method	Approach	Accuracy	Macro-F1	AUROC
SigLIP2 ZS	Zero-shot	68.7%	0.63	0.613
CLIP ZS	Zero-shot	49.7%	0.42	0.608
SigLIP2 LR	Reference	70.6%	0.62	0.844
DINOv3 kNN-5	Reference	69.3%	0.49	0.705
DINOv3 Proto	Reference	59.5%	0.45	0.675
Qwen VLM	VLM	56.4%	0.44	0.812

C. Upper Bound on Clean Imagery

On a ship inspection dataset [6] (317 close-range images, 5 classes), SigLIP2 zero-shot achieves 94.6% (vs. 68.7% on our data) and CLIP 88.6% (vs. 49.7%). The gap quantifies the domain shift from ship-spotter conditions to operational PTZ imagery at distances up to 10 km. This confirms recognition methods are capable. The challenge is data quality under operational conditions.

IV. DISCUSSION

The system achieves 70.6% type accuracy (SigLIP2 LR) as an operator pre-filter, with higher per-class accuracy for

Fig. 3. ROC curves for OOD detection (163 ID vs. 23 OOD crops). SigLIP2 LR achieves the best AUROC (0.844); Qwen VLM (0.812) shows strong OOD calibration despite lower classification accuracy.

visually distinctive types (container ships, passenger vessels). For security screening, false positives (flagging a legitimate vessel) are operationally acceptable as they trigger a brief operator review, while false negatives (missing a spoofed vessel) are the more critical concern.

The 30.6% bearing association precision is our most broadly relevant finding. It shows that automatic camera-AIS annotation can be unreliable in dense traffic and that prior evaluations using this approach likely understate recognition capability. Four factors compound the difficulty in our setup. (i) *Incomplete reception*: AIS was received through a small auxiliary antenna rather than the vessel’s primary navigation antenna, so some targets are missing. (ii) *Temporal misalignment*: the moving PTZ camera’s bearing must be time-synchronized to each frame, while AIS positions, transmitted only every few seconds to minutes, must be interpolated to the same instant, by which the vessel has moved. (iii) *No range*: the camera gives azimuth but no distance, so AIS targets sharing a bearing are indistinguishable, and depression-angle ranging is unreliable at 0.5–10 km, where the sub-degree angle is dominated by platform pitch and roll. (iv) *Traffic density*: the Weser estuary places many vessels at similar bearings. Even with fixed cameras, Gülsoylu et al. [5] report that panning alone significantly degrades association. Our set-level verification design avoids this problem entirely: rather than pairing individual detections to AIS targets, we compare type distributions.

The white-list approach maps naturally to existing security operations at multiple scales (per-port, per-zone, and fleet-level). Reference photographs can be obtained from vessel registries for any vessel with an MMSI or IMO number; the 39/50 vessel overlap between white-list and evaluation set reflects this intended deployment scenario. OOD detection (AUROC 0.844) enables flagging of unknown vessels, while zero-shot results (68.7%) establish type generalization for non-white-listed vessels.

Threat model: The system detects two categories of AIS anomalies: *type mismatches*, where a vessel’s visual type contradicts its AIS declaration (e.g., a tanker broadcasting as cargo), and *unknown vessels*, where a visual detection has no corresponding AIS entry or does not match any expected type. The system does not detect position spoofing (addressed by trajectory analysis) nor distinguish individual vessels of the same type.

Limitations: Three vessel types have ≤ 6 evaluation crops. The 9-class taxonomy is data-driven, not threat-driven. Fishing vessels, pleasure craft, and military vessels are absent. All data comes from one location; generalization remains to be validated, though the methods are pre-trained and not site-specific.

V. CONCLUSION

We presented a feasibility study for visual AIS type verification, a non-cooperative approach where camera imagery independently checks vessel types against AIS expectations. The three-stage pipeline (detection, type recognition, set-level

Fig. 4. Qualitative SigLIP2 LR predictions. Top (green): type matches. Middle (red): type mismatches. Bottom (orange): unknown vessels not matching any white-list type, shown with their confidence scores.

verification) avoids the unreliable per-vessel bearing matching that we show achieves only 30.6% precision, instead comparing type distributions at the set level.

The 94.6% upper bound on clean imagery confirms that current vision-language models have strong maritime type understanding; the 26 pp gap to operational performance (68.7%) is a data collection challenge, not a model limitation.

Looking ahead, decentralized deployment across vessels carrying cameras could create a non-cooperative AIS verification network complementing the cooperative AIS infrastructure. Many vessels already carry bridge cameras; SigLIP2 zero-shot at 68.7% runs on edge hardware with no vessel-specific data. An ongoing data collection campaign already addresses the antenna and PTZ synchronization limitations of this study, enabling larger datasets. Realizing the decentralized vision requires expansion to more vessel types and the institutional frameworks for multi-party verification data.

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